

DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF TOURISM VILLAGES IN KASHKADARYA REGION

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Abstract. *In the article, some aspects of the development of rural tourism in the Kashkadarya region, especially the natural and territorial conditions, were studied, and rural tourism is directly related to how the interaction between nature and man takes place. about the processes that took place. In our country, there are many places where tourists can relax and get healthy. Therefore, information was given about the fact that the mountainous and mountainous areas are unopened reserves for foreign tourists and their aspects in tourism.*

Keywords: *mountains, countryside, ecotourism, waterfalls, forests, rivers, caves, lakes.*

Introduction. The Kashkadarya region today is one of the regions of our country rich in the potential of natural, historical and socio - economic tourist - recreational resources, which serve as the basis for the development of almost all types of Tourism. It is known that the culture, traditions and lifestyle of the indigenous population of any country is the specific tourist potential of that place, and the important thing is not to miss it. By the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on measures for the further development of the tourism sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan“from November 1, 2019, the state committee for the development of tourism will begin to form a list of citizens ' assemblies with the highest tourism potential (urban, rural, villages and urban, urban, rural and village neighborhoods).[4]

Analysis of thematic literature (Literature review). A lot of scientific research is devoted to the scientific and theoretical issues of tourism, including many studies of scientists from our republic and foreign countries. sources about tourism from foreign scientists V.Huntsiker, K.Krapf, R.Barton, P.Deferham, W.S.Pereobrazhensky, N.N.Miroshnichenko, L.I.Mukhin, and in the works of the A.Taxanovs, in our republic A.N.Nigmatov, N.T.Shamuratova, B.Kamolov, M.Khoshimov, S.N.Abduvohidov, K.S.Yasharev, J.Yu.Khasanov, X.Jumayev studied by. Research methodology. The Kashkadarya region is also unique in tourism. In the Area survey R.Davidov, A.V.Drozdov, V.V.Khrabovchenko, T.V.Bochkaryova, L.I.Egorenkov, A.Taksanov, A.N.Nigmatov, N.T.Shamuratova, B.Kamolov, M.Khoshimov, S.N.Abduvohidov, K.S.Yasharev, R.Usmanova, X. Jumaev. We took as a methodological basis the research work performed by the and other authors in this area. The top tourist destinations include national parks, desert areas, mountains, lakes, and cultural facilities in developing countries in particular, most of which are in rural areas. Rural tourism has a beautiful natural environment and a unique cultural heritage. As a result, we can say that the factors affecting the development of rural tourism are present throughout our republic.

Analysis and results. The basis of the practice of rural tourism is a rural settlement, where ancient customs and traditions, as well as various folk elements, ethnographic masterpieces are preserved, which can be achieved and well used if used in harmony with a strong strategy of their promotion.[21] Rural tourism is primarily aimed at urban residents living in stressful environments, as well as people with moderate incomes. The purpose of establishing a tourism

village is to further develop the tourism potential of the area, further increase the flow of tourists, to introduce tourists to the unique tourist potential of the area and the objects of cultural heritage, to create conditions favorable to tourists.[19] It consists in ensuring the consistent development of modern tourism infrastructure in the region, expanding the types of Tourism, Hotel and transport services provided in accordance with modern requirements, improving the quality and assisting business entities wishing to operate in this area, activating domestic tourism, creating new jobs.[13] Through the development and promotion of rural tourism, it has a positive effect, especially on the development of the village on the one hand and its inhabitants on the other. These benefits affect agriculture, transportation, food and various services. Thus, tourism is an important feature of the rural economy in these specific areas.[20] For information, in the regions of citizens' gatherings by Decree No. 5781 of the president, provided that no less than 20 family guest houses are created, and at least five different types of services (except for living and or feeding services) are provided for tourists, they are given the status of "Tourism quarter", "Tourism Village" or "tourism Oval". As of 2020, the granted Citizens Assembly of the status of "Tourism neighborhood", "Tourism Village" or "tourism Oval" "will be included in the state programs" prosperous village "and" prosperous neighborhood".[4]. The first-line tasks in the development of rural tourism are of course the means of placement. But in the initial entrepreneurship in the development of rural tourism in the villages, this issue can be solved quickly.[24] Developed rural tourism, with European states offering a rental method in accommodating tourists even at an early time. After the development of entrepreneurship, the construction of individual houses, cottages begins as a result of competition.[21] But the first activities in the development of rural tourism should begin with the development of tourist routes to the most attractive and interesting tourist resources in rural areas. Because the tourist flow all the time begins to form after the tourist route and its advertising. The development of a tourist route to the villages is also the most favorable opportunities for the development of rural tourism. Because, the opportunities for the development of tourist routes in the villages are both numerous, and the topics are numerous, and the diversity of tourist resources and the potential of covering almost all types of Tourism. In the development of rural tourism, the following stages of the development of tourist routes can be developed.

1. Study of nature in villages-ecological tourism routes.
2. Cultural heritage study routes in villages ethnographic tourism routes.
3. Routes of study of historical and archaeological sites in villages historical - cultural tourism routes.
4. Shrines in villages, religious pilgrimage routes.
5. Agricultural, horticultural and animal husbandry studies in villages-agrotourism routes.
6. Study of folk National Games in villages-national spiritual cultural tourism routes.
7. Study of national culture and national folklore in villages-cultural tourism routes.
8. Agrotourism routes to study the life of farmers in the villages.

One of the advantages of rural tourism is that it is based on local tourism, initiatives are based on local management, local specifics, based on the local landscape and affecting the local culture. In theory, the focus on the local contributes to regional development.[20] At the same time, large-scale measures are being implemented for the development of ecotourism in the villages, the ecological direction is justified by the processes of developing the environmental consciousness of the population of the country and the demand of incoming tourists for environmentally meaningful trips.[17] It is promising to organize an ecological path of various

content, conduct active environmental events in the places where rural guest houses are most concentrated.[24] For tourists, it is advisable to conduct master classes on the preparation of natural products, national dishes of the village, to demonstrate customs, to get acquainted with the ancient methods of livestock, gardening and farming in the direction of agrotourism. The organization of recreation areas on the slopes of the mountains serves a meaningful recreation of tourists, in particular. the goal of "rural tourism" is to increase the net profit of the rural population and increase their participation in the development of the tourism product.[4] The main objectives of the imaging strategies are to attract tourism costs, create jobs in tourism and related industries, form positive images for a potential investor and local population and provide an environment that attracts and maintains professionals who make up the main workforce, for which many benefits are being applied by the state. In 2022, 40 billion soums were allocated to the region for the establishment of family guest houses, hostels, a fire camp complex, autocampings, an eco-complex, container towns and tent camps, funded under the program for the development of family entrepreneurship for the development of the services sector and their renovation projects.[23] In accordance with the relevant decision of the president, up to 50 million rubles for family guest houses, up to 1 billion rubles for hostels, up to 300 million rubles for a complex of fire camps, up to 3 billion rubles for autocampings, up to Rs 600 crore for container towns, up to Rs 60 crore for tent camps and are directed to finance renovation projects, with commercial banks providing loans at a rate of Rs 14 per cent for a period of up to 5 years to implement these projects.[24] In addition, according to the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, PQ-212 of 19.04.2022, loans are allocated to tourism development projects at an annual rate of 14 percent for a period of up to 5 years, in which the amount of credit depends on the activities of the business entity, the maximum amount is given up to 5 billion soums.[15] Examples include up to Rs 50 crore in rural guest house establishment, up to Rs 300 crore in fire camps and eco houses, up to Rs 300 crore in tent camp construction. Entrepreneurs who have established guest houses, catering and outlets, entertainment venues in tourist villages pay a tax and social tax on their working capital for 3 years at a rate of 1 percent, property, land, water taxes only 1 percent of the calculated amount.[23] It is noted that residents of Taragai and Langar villages in the Chirochi district took the initiative to establish guest houses from at least 100. Currently, the work of the project has begun, according to the project, a series of tourist facilities will be created in Taragai, a unique historical and macro-residential area for a year. In particular, in the village will be installed modern stella, a selfie zone, sanitary hygiene facilities, Ecological Waste Boxes. The 15 kilometres of road leading to the Tourism Village will be repaired, improving electricity, drinking water and running water and communication and informatization systems. A new information center will be established. Changes in the tourism village "Taragay" primarily covered the goal of improving the lifestyle of the population of the region and, of course, further increasing the flow of tourists to an area rich in historical monuments, unique values. Now every year, 200 young people of tourism villages are taught at the expense of the budget for free in tourism technical schools. For 2.5 thousand projects in 135 specialized neighborhoods, 250 billion soums and 50 million will be allocated in the same year.[20] There are a number of major projects aimed at making the reserve one of the world's tourist centers. Any successful development of Tourism, whether in the village or not, will depend on commercial, economic and logistical issues, namely product quality, ease of access and infrastructure, availability and investor interest. In many of these aspects, rural areas may be at a disadvantage compared to urbanized and developed areas.[13] These problems can be caused by

political and institutional barriers, particularly in developing countries, i.e. the administrative complexity of working with sparsely populated areas, the lack of dialogue between rural development and Tourism Development, and low-level priority on rural areas by the center.[14] So in order to solve these problems, 60 billion from the budget for the construction of road infrastructure and the weighing of high-speed internet. the Sum is channeled. For information, in the process of acquaintance with social cultural objects in the Kashkadarya region, the head of the country gave instructions to objectively study the situation of historical and cultural monuments dating back to the Timurid period in the village of “Katta Langar” and develop a scientific concept on their eternal preservation, make a proposal for repair work.[23] The "Maidanak" Observatory, a world-renowned and unique "Maidanak" Observatory and a 14th-century shrine and mosque in the Kamashi district, is intended to attract tourists from all over the world. A working group was formed and fully acquainted with the mosque, the historical and cultural object of the large anchor, where it expressed the need to develop a concept of proper repair, taking into account the opinion of such halgar organizations as UNESCO, IKOMOS, as well as the amazing maiolikas, mosaics, wooden dormitories, epigraphics.[24] It should be noted that on the initiative of our Honorable President, a large anchor Koran kept in the Office of Muslims of Uzbekistan was restored. The restoration of the pages of Mushaf was carried out in three stages, namely in 2019, 2020 and 2021, with the participation of restorers of the Louvre Museum of France and local specialists, under the auspices of the foundation for the development of Culture and art under the Ministry of Culture. The Islamic art exhibition in Jeddah is an important international event that allows you to showcase projects related to this rare culture. The exhibits displayed by our country will not only increase the interest of the world community in their study, but will also lead to an increase in the number of foreign tourists visiting the large Anchor Village.[23] You have a message that from November 24, 2022, the past year to March 6, 2023, the Cabinet of Ministers, in charge of the foundation for the development of Culture and art, will present at the Louvre Museum of France “treasures of the oases of Uzbekistan. At the crossroads of caravan routes”. In it, two sheets of 13 pages of the “great anchor Koran”, which were restored by Louvre specialists, held in the library foundation of the Muslim Office of Uzbekistan, were shown at the exhibition in the Louvre Museum. The purpose of this is that the demonstrations organized by Uzbekistan in Paris will allow millions of citizens around the world to see this great history with their own eyes. Experts believe that these demonstrations will be very effective, since cooperation in the field of Culture quickly introduced the country and people to the world. France is visited by 60 million tourists a year and the Louvre by more than 10 million. The presentation of Uzbekistan in such a large-scale exhibition will not only more closely introduce the history of our country, but will also serve to further increase interest in our country, its culture and history.[20] It also serves as a kind of promotion for the development of Tourism. The better people get to know each other through exhibitions, interaction, the more mutual trust increases. Trust, on the other hand, provides tremendous opportunities for other areas of cooperation. From January 23 to April 23 of the same year, the first exhibition on Islamic art will be held in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. At the exhibition, representatives of several organizations headed by the foundation for the development of Culture and art of the Republic of Uzbekistan will introduce the historical heritage of Uzbekistan to the participants. 17 exhibits of Uzbekistan will be shown at the international event. Four pages of the large anchor Qur'an, one of the oldest Mushaf manuscripts in the Library Museum of the Muslim Office of Uzbekistan, are presented, two of which are the first to be brought to public attention.

The aim of the exhibition, organized by the Saudi Ministry of Culture and the Diriy biennale Foundation, is to connect past, present and future.[22] within the Ministry of Culture, proposals were put forward to establish a complex of “great anchor cultural heritage” and to beautify the village in accordance with international and local tourism. There are many historical, archaeological foundations for the fact that the site is a tabarruk step. One article in the “Turkestanskiye vedomosti”, dated August 24, 1920, reads The “Anchor Village” was also a town in the past. This village has maintained its cultural status. It is not far from Yakkabag. Of course there will be paved roads instead of horse trails on these lands. The tombstones standing in the churchyard testify that the anchor is not an ordinary village. They are incredibly decorated.[23] 38 kilometers of road leading to these facilities will be repaired, and home hotels and restaurants will be established. At the same time, the tourist-recreational zone “Maidanak” is organized. Relevant studies are conducted on this issue by the Republican working group headed by the Ministry of Tourism and sports. The road, power supply, water and wastewater infrastructure up to the “Maidanak” observatory site, 176 km from Qarshi, is currently being studied and a related project is being developed. Scientific research institution of the Institute of Astronomy of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. The book enters the complex of a high mountain Observatory. Kashkadarya region is located on the western tip of Maidanak mountain on the border of Kamashi districts of Yakkabag.[7] the height above sea level is 2650 meters, with a total area of 40 hectares. The diameter of the mirrors of the telescopes installed in the observatory is 1.5 and 1.0 meters. In addition to these, 4 telescopes with a mirror diameter of 60 cm and 3 telescopes with a diameter of 50 cm were installed. The Observatory collects data from variable star photometry located in the fields of the North Pole of our galaxy and in the nebulae around the solar system, photometric effects of weak changes in the brightness of stars were found.[16] The Observatory conducts research on rare objects-gravitational lenses, quasars, and active-core galaxies located at the farthest, edges of the universe. Kamashi is under the district forestry, Yegrisuv 1st forest department, for incoming tourists, pastures have been built by entrepreneurs. During 2022, a modern type of guest house will be built next to the Maidanak Observatory.[10] Experts in the field visited the Maidanak Observatory and discussed the placement of firewood, “camping”, “glamping”, eco - houses, containers of light construction in the 7,900-hectare areas of the Maidanak mountains.[7] In addition, it is possible to establish more than 100 guest houses in the villages of Kukbulok, Urtadara, Chukurkishlok, Kattaura, Bogabod, develop mountain bike and extreme tourism services in the area by diversifying the services provided, at the same time it is possible to admit that it is planned to build osma dor Road, 3-star hotel and wellness complexes. At the same time, new projects for the development of tourism will be carried out on the territory of the latitudinal station, which is located 65 kilometers from this address. To do this, the total repair of the roads leading to the area received from the budget of the Republic 40 billion. the sum is allocated.[20] A waterfall of the same name can be seen near the village of Suvtushar, Shahrisabz district. It is located in the Hisor Reserve and flows from an altitude of 2100 meters above sea level into the river. Such beauty cannot be overlooked, the fact that a noisy stream of water turns into foam looks especially impressive in summer.[18] But even in winter, the waterfall does not lose its beauty, because it often does not freeze, and against the background of mountains covered with soft snow, it acquires a special charm.[9] Since March 8, 2022, the decision of the government on the correctness of measures to effectively use the tourism potential of Kashkadarya region has been adopted.[5] in accordance with it, ethnotourism will be organized in the villages

of Gilan and Kul, and 5 guest houses will be built in each village. Foreign guests will remember for a long time their trips to the mountain villages of Kul and Gilan. That being said, until 2018 they were closed to the public due to a special border regime. But the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 20, 2019 PQ-4247 “on measures to improve the system of Public Administration in the field of protected nature areas”. [3] It was also possible to organize the work of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the implementation of the order of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1599-XX of February 6, 2018 to change the nature reserve status (from the regime of the protected zone) on certain plots of the reserve for the development of environmental tourism. The lake and Gilan are separated from the city center of Shahrizabz by the fact that it is located in the mountains at an altitude of 2400-2600 meters above sea level. Life in these villages is strikingly different from that of ordinary villages and settlements. [10] Most of the population does not leave the village for a lifetime, so life here has not destroyed the same natural appearance as it was 100 or more years ago. This is also considered much more interesting for tourists. [17] the popularity of the Lake Village is that it is located on the threshold of Hazrati Sultan peak, the highest point in Uzbekistan. Closed until recently and opened to travelers again in recent years, it is thanks to the fact that the climbers pass through the village of the lake that the fullness of the malum opportunity here may be delighted with the way of living of the Mahali population and the charming nature of the village itself. [12] Local residents drive through the streets mainly in motorcycles and old Uases. There is a wide opportunity for tourists to plunge into this place at least temporarily into a world without noise, IP television and the internet from skyscrapers, cars and factories. In the villages of Gilan and Kul, guests get acquainted not only with the life of the village, but also with its customs. For example, wedding ceremonies here are still held on the basis of old Uzbek customs (Muslim Sharia). As a rule, girls are married immediately after adulthood. The houses in Gilan are mostly two-storey, with the first floor adapted for domestic needs and livestock. The owners live on the second floor. You will not see Gates, large obstacles, either in Gilan or in the Kul. People live here like a big family. [13] If we talk about the topographic location of villages, then you can hardly find a flat earth surface in them. The whole life here is on steep slopes. They also grow vegetables and fruits. Tourists who come here are happy to taste national dishes, admiring the skills of local residents. For example, few people know that bread with a diameter of 1 meter is still baked in these villages. They have not forgotten the recipes for ancient dishes, including “lotingon”, “koch”, “qurtoba” (which is made from dried). The main ingredient in these dishes is sour milk and meat. The composition is rich and high-calorie, keeping them full for a long time, whether it is a shepherd or a farmer. Interestingly, people go to Gilan not only for originality, but also for extreme cases, because recently a sport rafting was organized here on the rafting mountain river. This interesting adventure full of adrenaline attracts not only foreign guests, but also residents of Uzbekistan. Agrotourism activities were established in the villages of Varganza and Hazrati Bashir. Pomegranate festivals are held as part of this line. [24] For reference, the village of “Varganza” in Kashkadarya is the first agrotourism village in the province”. It was the site of the first ever “Anor” international agrotourism festival in 2019, and the village was given the status of an “agrotourism village”. Varganza pomegranates are famous all over the world. Its varieties are also popular in the international market. Guests, who also had a large number of foreigners among the local population, were greeted by the villagers on a festive occasion. From the very first steps towards the festival resort, a special vigor is felt in the person, the doors of the houses are wide open, the

locals invited tourists with unique compositions made of pomegranate, grapes, national costumes. During the Festival, tourists are offered to taste several varieties of pomegranate, freshly squeezed juices, national confectionery and much more. The purpose of the festival is to effectively use the tourism potential of the Kashkadarya region, preserve and elevate rich cultural heritage and historical traditions, to provide comprehensive support to citizens engaged in National Handicrafts and gardening, as well as to develop agriculture.[20] According to legends, the first pomegranate was originally planted by the Lord Bashir ota near the spring of Karabakh in the foothills of Kyzylkia. Hazrati Bashir ota gave pomegranate seedlings to those who sought shelter from him and showed the planting site of the seedling in the village of Varganza. As he drew a line with his staff from Kashkadarya to Varganza, he ordered to dig a ditch here, and advised that pomegranate was a pledge of the well-being of the population, to cultivate it there. A few days before the opening of the Festival, the organizers build a stage in the center of the village - in the middle of the gardens, for performances, there were tapchans, exhibition stands with samples of folk applied art of local residents, and, of course, there were ripe pomegranate mountains everywhere. In one case, these fruits were arranged in a pyramid shape, in another they were displayed in baskets woven on tree branches, and in the third they became part of the stage design. And the fact that here several villagers skillfully demonstrate pomegranate cutting to their masters is very interesting for the fans of agrotourism who visit here. It is not for nothing that the mountain village, with its charming Air, clear spring waters, has long attracted people, the oldest human addresses are also in mountain villages.[16] Of course, hardworking farmers made Varganza pomegranate especially tasty and well-known. Our compatriots are happy to buy pomegranate from the markets from this mountain village. It is possible that the representatives of UNESCO are participating in the seminar, listening to our folk songs and dances in the village of Varganza agro, to get a bakhramand from handicrafts and, of course, pomegranate water. Together with this, the village of "Bashir" is being transformed into a tourism village. The shrine of "Hazrati Bashir" is located in this village. The name of the shrine is associated with the name of the saint Hazrat Sultan Said Ahmad Bashir (1368-1464), who lived in this place. It should be noted that in 2022, more than 400,000 domestic and foreign tourists visit the Hazrati Bashir shrine. This residence has attracted attention not only for its unique nature, but also for its unique history. According to various sources, Khoja Hasan, the father of Hazrati Sultan Said Ahmad Bashir, was 90 years old and their mother Bibi Malahat was not a child, despite being 80 years old. One day Said Ne'matullah, the brother of said Baraka, the saint of Amir Temur, who had made his way to this side, prays for them. Soon the prayer is answered and the Hazrati Bashir is born. However, milk does not come from an elderly mother. The baby begins to be called "Beshir" (without milk) by those around him. By the miracle of God, a chalice appears under a large maple in their courtyard, from which milk flows until the child passes the age of breastfeeding. This cup is still known for its icy, tip-clear water and healing properties even in cancer.[22] It should be noted that most tourists who come to the shrine, of course, drink this water and take it with them too. Hazrati Bashir is buried in Niyoztepa in the village. A local legend goes that "the fir tree in front of the Tomb of Hazrati Bashir was that person's staff". It is said that the Lord Bashir threw his father's staff and said, "Wherever he goes, there will be my grave". The staff is pinned to the ground with the large side. Therefore, unlike other trees, its lower side is thin, the upper side is creamy. Even this talisman will definitely not leave tourists indifferent. The village of "Hazrati Bashir" is located on the Kashkadarya River. The tall plantains give the village its splendour.[8] The area is also contiguous

with mountains. Therefore, travelers from different regions of our country and foreign countries come here during the summer months.[18] they rest by the river while visiting their Lord Bashir ota. The village has developed pilgrimage tourism, ecotourism and agrotourism. It is worth noting that in the current year, a number of works are being carried out to bring the number of tourists visiting the village to 700 thousand, and to turn the village into a tourist village. More than 20 family guest houses now operate in the village.[20] It allows foreign and domestic tourists to stay in the area more and get to know the local folk lifestyle more closely. There is no doubt that the lush nature, the clear mountain air, the healing chalice, and the springs attract tourists to the hospitable Village People, the environmentally friendly fruits, the welcoming food and the shrine that gives peace to the hearts.[8] from another soulim village of Kitab district, Kaynar and Jausdir, 1.5 km in the mountainous village of Kaynar, which borders the Samarkand region of Kitab district, with the participation of Turkish investors. lik dor road will be built. The number of tourist attractions in the area also increases. In particular, special functional and seasonal recreational zones will be created, providing the facilities of modern tourism infrastructure (hotel complexes, cultural-wellness, commercial-entertainment and other facilities of tourist importance), the necessary conditions for serving tourists.[19] The weather and nature of the area have always entertained passengers, but when we take advantage of the opportunity created by our President and turn this destination into an ecotourism destination while preserving the beauty of nature, we will have done a great job for our residents and visitors alike.[10] because, as a result of this, 1,500 additional jobs will be created in the village of Kaynar alone. Traveling through the village of Jaus, you believe that the tradition of the population, lifestyle, ancient rasmrusums, legends, ancient Turkestan architecture have so far arrived in its pure form without change. The main part of the village is occupied by houses with flat clay roofs, the front part of which is decorated with embossed columns, typical of ancient Muslim architecture.[19] Since these houses are built on slopes, often the roof of the former serves as a courtyard for the latter, and from a distance these buildings look like multi-storey houses. If you pay attention to household utensils in the Yards, you will get your eyes on the jugs, muesli, ancient urchins, oil-bearing cubes, cobs on the walls, many of which have been used since past times. This law is broken by several new houses built in the current style at the entrance to the village, covered with a superstructure. They are houses that were moved after the surilmas that took place on the outskirts of the village. According to the local population, the village is around 1,600-1,900 years old, and it stretches for up to three kilometers along the Right Bank of the Jinnidarya. Extreme ecotourism activities are organized in the villages of Tatar, Zarmas and Toshkurgon, located in Yakkabog district. The village of Toshkurgon and its surroundings are rich in rare nature monuments of the Hisor Reserve, and are counted from naturally interesting addresses.[18] at the same time, both routes to The Spit pass along the mountains with a very attractive rangin landscape of the rugged mountain and mountainous part, where the influence of human relations with nature is evident.[8] At the same time, both the Yakkabog-Toshkurgan road and the anchor-Toshkur road are counted from the roads where there is access to vehicles.[10] The Spit is a village of a unique structure built 500-600 years ago at an altitude of 1900-1950 meters above sea level. The country houses are mostly two storeys, with a morgue and barn below, a high attic on the second floor, a door, and front pilasters consisting of naïve porch houses.[9] The shelf is decorated with floral wood with a ceiling. The streets of the wide village are flat but curved-the streets of bugri go to the squares and adjoin them. The quarry has a very beautiful machite built 250 years ago. According to the floral decoration of Naqishli,

this is a rare monument of machit Oriental architecture. The population of machites of the same type in the village was tortta. Of these, two were broken 50-60 years ago, and one was destroyed by neglect between the coming years.[20] Well, this settlement, which has long been famous for its blacksmithing, Masters, would become a kind of settlement within the Reserve as an example of the memorialization of the mountain villages of South Uzbekistan.[15] Located near the shallow village, at the end of the Qal'ai - sheron saddle, on a high, bluish stone rock, the largest 50-45 cm from the Jurassic measures up to 90-100 meters, and there are 31 dinosaur tracks that have survived to the present day. In 1975, in this number of scientific studies, brogan, a Moscow-based geographer scientist, was awarded the title of Academician These tracks were identified by V.I.Rasek as belonging to dinosaurs that lived between 190 and 195 million years ago.[8] Dinosaur tracks and other geological monuments have unparalleled significance in understanding the progress of our country hundreds of millions of years ago. It is this Kalasoy basin that is characterized by the presence of its incredibly interesting geological objects.[7] the terms Qalaso, Qamadaryo, Qalaisheron, Lion Castle also indicate that the valley of this river flows from other valleys, forming a narrow and deep gorge. Indeed, the Kalasoy River is known and famous as an amazing huge-sized Valley. From a height of 40-140 meters above the river bed, the steep Devoir of the gorge begins.[9] The height of the walls of the tank, which in some places also have flat racks resembling narrow soup, is 150-300 meters. Hukizburun waterfall, on the Right Bank of the Qal'ai-Sheron sound, 2000 meters above sea level, is located at an altitude of. Two reminiscent of the nose of an abscess from a steep rock, each 75-80 cm in diameter. the water that flows out of the hole in which it is, splits in half and runs down from a height of 35 meters in the form of a fountain, hitting the surface of rocky cliffs and flowing out forms a unique natural landscape.[10] At the top of the Sarituz saddle, which begins at 1600 meters above sea level in the Sarituz latitudes, there is the Okkamar waterfall, which rises at 1500 meters above sea level, more than 100 meters in length, only in the spring months (seasonally) from melted snow, rain, spring waters. The waterfall flows through the fertile cut stones of the Sarituz shade in the direction of the snake trail, with its playful movements, downward, giving a wonderful view of nature.[13] Fast-flowing water particles reminiscent of a snake that is about to burst into its prey, which flows from rock to rock, provide moisture to endemic plants that grow on this earth. These plants will become an integral part of the natural landscape, not only giving a special beauty to this place. For the convenience of visiting foreign and domestic tourists in these villages. 5 Guest Houses, 5 campsites and 10 lawns will be built. Modern guest houses, which are being built by Kesh Rubin tur LLC in the Tatar neighborhood, can be put into use during the summer tourist season. An ethnocultural Emir Temur Warriors military training camp will be built.[20] Also, ecological tourism in Sarchashma and Suvtushar villages, astronomical tourism routes will be established on the territory of the book latitudinal station. In Central Asia, Earth motion testing is focused on monitoring tectonic shifts in the Earth's crust. The book named after Mirzo Ulugbek began with the establishment and activities of the Observatory of international breadth. When taking a geographical map, only the book District is the only populated place on the territory of Uzbekistan that passes on the international parallel (39 degrees 08 minutes). That is why it was decided to build an observatory of international latitude on the territory of the book District. In September 1928, the Bamberg zenit - telescope and Short clock were obtained from Germany. On November 14, 1930, the first observation began and continues continuously to this day.[16] Work was also not interrupted during World War II. In those years, a minor planet was discovered here, named.

At the suggestion of the 1st president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the planet was given the name “Samarkand”, the ancient and navqiran city of the Republic. Of the more than 200 observatories that exist in the world, only five are of particular importance. It is gratifying that the international latitude Station” book " has entered this top five. Today, a unique structure is being built on its territory, which the astropark does not resemble in Central Asia. "Our astropark will be the first park in Uzbekistan, it works only at night.[23] Visitors will be able to see Saturn or the moon with their own eyes after 10 am. On the territory of the garden, three museums, a gallery and a 3D cinema are being organized, in which Video Films telling about the importance of galaxies are shown. Despite the fact that the Astropark has not yet been officially opened, guests can visit it and enjoy the unique object of astronomy,” within the framework of this direction, scientific and practical conferences and seminars dedicated to the heritage of Amir Temur and the art of creativity will be held. In the village of Pomuk, Jeynov and Mirishkor, Mirishkor district, there is enough opportunity for the development of National Crafts, ethnotourism. "Jeynov" has a tourist village and tourist projects that meet modern requirements in this area. When we were in the village of Pomuq we talked here with ethnic Turkmens who migrated from Turkmenistan several centuries ago. Turkmen is spoken in the village.[13] The Turkmen language spoken in pomuk is very close to Uzbek. Its main dialect is Tekin (Teke). This is interesting for visiting turis, Turkmens currently residing in Pomuk have kept their customs, traditions. The Turkmen national cultural centre operates here and a folklore community has also been established under it. Many were interested in the processes associated with carpets woven in pomuk, especially among them the so-called “girl carpet”. This tradition still exists today.[22] Each and every part of this carpet has excess, around 20 centimeters of threads sticking out. Local residents say that now a child who begins to walk learns to get up and walk, from these threads. It is difficult to meet such traditions in other parts of the world. One such shrine in the district of Dehkanabad has a natural lake known as Khojpok ota, which is located in the south of the district is now unsuitable for drinking brine from it. In the composition of Mineral water and healing mud, sulfides, various salts, 42 types of minorelements are found, the lake area of 0.1 kilom square mineral water leaks from a depth of 47 m. The total area of the Muddy lake mine is 2.5 kilom square.[13] On the mountainside next to the village, the spring boils, and with the end of the spring months, the hot summer heat begins, a huge number of pilgrims come from the entire territory of our republic, especially in the regions of Surkhandarya, Kashkadarya, Samarkand, Jizzakh. In the village of Xujaipok, the mineral Muddy Lake is visited by 15 thousand vacationers, the water of this spring is distinguished by its unique healing, which improves the liver, gastrointestinal, gastric activity of people who drink it, and provides great support in recovery.

Again, this will correct various rashes and skin diseases using salt water. There is also mucus, which is also a cure for joint diseases and various colds. This is why in recent years the number of visitors here is increasing, with a tourist project planned for the Hojaipok shrine. The formation of entrepreneurial projects is being carried out in the villages of “Xujaipok” and “Buztepa”, which border the Turkmen Republic of the district of Dehkanabad.[12] There are plans to establish a tourist zone next to the natural lake of the Xujaipok shrine. In this case, it was recommended to organize a sanatorium, catering, department stores and parking clean drinking water. As a result, I thought-deep roads will improve the number of people who came here was above. Together with this, new jobs will be created for 42 citizens with additional income of local residents, favorable conditions will be created for them, as well as for visiting guests. The development of ecotourism

is considered promising here. The Konsoy Salt Lake is located 16 km southeast of the center of the peasant District, 10 km from the magistrantal road between the mountains at an altitude of 1260 m above sea level, and about 8 thousand vacationers visit every year. The water consumption of the lake is 1.5-2.0 liters per second, the mineralization rate is 266 grams, the water content is Chloride-Sodium, the temperature is 34 degrees. This water slurry has been used in the Kyzyltepa sanatorium.[13] It was recommended that the lakeside healers establish service networks and turn the surroundings into a treatment area following sanitary regulations as a result of greening, landscaping, highway construction, and establish public catering, department store guest houses and parking clean drinking water. At the same time, there is an opportunity to create about 100 seasonal and permanent jobs in these settlements by providing services and establishing a service network on the basis of state-owned partnerships. Sahibqiran Amir Temur was born, Yakkabag district, Xujailgor village was being overlooked. Now this village is also being transformed into a prosperous village. There are dozens of steps associated with Hazrat Amir Temur in this village which is much more convenient for ecotourism and pilgrimage tourism. The spring from which the water was taken when the man was born still has healing water, where the 100-kilo stone that our grandfather trained in his youth was preserved. He went to the caves where he trained with his young men.[20] Well, there are only sources that attract tourists. As a result of beautification in order to attract more tourists, 214 house hotels and 9 hostels will be established in the region. As a result, the number of domestic tourists will be increased to 1 million 250 thousand, the number of foreign tourists to 200 thousand, the number of hotels to 50, the number of tour operators and turagents to 20.[24] The "Halal tourism center", which serves visiting tourists, will be established in historical monuments and holy steps and shrines in the region, and large-scale propaganda forums, religious competitions and Pilgrimage Festivals will be organized on the territory of the shrines. Pilgrimage tourism has developed in Qarshi district, including the memorial complex "Abul - Mu'in an - Nasafi", located in the village of Qavchin, whose history is painted with thousands of years. Tombstones decorated with mulberry trees, ancient scrolls, whose Scrolls flow from centuries, are a clear example of this. The mausoleum of the great scholar, hazrat Abul Muin an-Nasafi, as well as the mosque named after him have been preserved in kadamjo. In order to create favorable conditions for pilgrims coming to the Holy step, large - scale construction and repair and reconstruction work was carried out on this facility. In particular, a large Jome mosque was built, designed for 600 seats. This mosque has all the modern amenities and all the conditions are created for our praying citizens who come here.[22] In addition, the mausoleum, where hazrat Abul Muin an-Nasafi died, was completely reconstructed. The complex covered an area of about 1.5 hectares. In addition, a library with a large Book Fund and a magnificent study hall were completed inside the complex. This gives the library a wide opportunity to take advantage of the collection of books in Uzbek and Arabic, aimed at a wide audience of readers. During the renovation of Abul Muin an-Nasafi shrine, special emphasis was placed on preserving the historical identity while providing extensive facilities for visitors to the shrine. the potential for the development of pilgrimage tourism in shrines is high. a clear plan of measures has been set out to eliminate the shortcomings identified as a result and create additional conditions for pilgrims, increase the number of tourists visiting the region's pilgrimage facilities. Located in the same district, the village of Shilvi is considered the settlement where the Highness of Sheikh Shibli lived. On the eastern side of the village is a historical monument dating back to the 18th century, the Shrine of Shaykh - Shibli.[13] It contains the symbolic tomb of Sheikh Abu Bakr Muhammad

ibn Halab Shibli. A huge mosque is standing near the Tomb. The roof of the mosque is closed in the style of wooden architecture. The solitary column in the middle is given quality processing and shape. The logs are joined to this column on four sides. The vassals were worked with taste and dialed in pairs. The roof vases and woodwork were patterned in their day with natural color paints. Three sides of the mosque are surrounded by a porch. The awnings are supported by nine huge pillars. The structure of the tarkh of the mosque building indicates that it was one of the main shrines in this surrounding area in its time. The Department for the development of pilgrimage tourism is conducting an out-of-Area Study. During the study and monitoring work, it is also possible to use the irrigation networks injection trunk canal as recreational resources, in which the identified shortcomings and measures to be taken in the future are established, proposals and recommendations are developed. A tourism complex “Chaman” will be built on the banks of the Kashkadarya River, flowing from the territory of the district. [20]

It can be argued that in place of the Conclusion. Experience in the development of rural tourism in the Kashkadarya region shows that historical-cultural regions mainly have certain signs of stability. On the one hand, rural tourism serves to increase the viability of tourist destinations by ensuring employment, increasing production and, in general, increasing the standard of living of the population. On the other hand, the income from tourist services provided by a large number of guest houses leads to an increase. Due to the low density of tourist flows, the ecological balance of natural systems is not disturbed, biodiversity is maintained, the appearance of waste and environmental pollution are minimized. The ethnographic features of the territory are inextricably linked with rural tourism, thanks to which local communities, traditions and culture are preserved and actively developed. It also makes it possible to preserve the historical heritage of local history museums that actively participate in the tourist product, to collect data or conduct observation work over plants and animals, organizing excursions to local history museums, zoobogs, Botanical Gardens, dendrariums that arouse primary data, samples, layouts, photos, tables, mapping and other interest (on the problems of Nature use and conservation). Because it contributes to solving major socio-economic problems and allows for the sustainable development of rural areas. The only way to develop the village is to encourage rural tourism. Tourism gives small entrepreneurs many opportunities to contribute to providing a tourism experience to generate financial income. These possibilities occur in both the formal and informal sectors, but in fact the difference between the two can be blurred. If government assistance is well promoted, tourism and rural tourism will develop the amount of visitors will increase. This leads to economic development in rural areas at the expense of Tourism.

REFERENCES

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Шавкат Мирзиёевнинг Бутунжаҳон туризм ташкилоти Бош Ассамблеяси 25-сессиясидаги нутқи 16.10.2023 у
2. Mirziyoev Sh.M. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2018 yil 28 dekabrda Oliy Majlisga Murojaatnomasi.// Yoshlar ovozi. 2018 yil, 29 dekabr. № 148 (16305).
3. Mirziyoev Sh.M. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019 yil 20 martdagi PQ-4247-sonli “Qo‘riqlanadigan tabiat hududlari sohasida davlat boshqaruvi tizimini takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi Qarori.

4. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентнинг 2019 йил 1 -ноябидан “Ўзбекистон Республикасида туризм соҳасини янада ривожлантириш чора тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги Фармони Халқ сўзи 2019 йил 14 - август
5. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Вазирлар Маҳкамасининг 2019 йил 8 мартдаги ”Қашқадарё вилоятининг туризм салоҳиятидан самарали фойдаланиш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида” 198-сонли Қарори.
6. Абдуллаев С.И., Усмонова Р. Қашқадарё ҳавзаси текислик қисми ландшафтларни табақалашуви // Ўзбекистон География жамияти ахбороти. 23-жилд. –Тошкент, 2003. - Б. 37-38.
7. Абдуллаев С.И., Усмонова Р. Қашқадарё ландшафтларини тасниф қилишнинг айрим масалалари //Жанубий Ўзбекистон табиат манбаларидан оқилона фойдаланиш масалалари. -Т., 1997. –Б. 22-27.
8. Маматов А. М Абдуллаев С. И Хўжамқулов Б. Е Ҳисор давлат қўриқхонаси- Ўрта Осиё тоғ табиатининг андозаси. Илмий оммабоп нашир Қарши. “Насаф” нашриёти 2010. у
9. Маматов А.М. Ҳисор тоғлар баландлик ландшафт комплексларини муҳофаза қилишнинг долзарб масалалари //География ва табиий ресурслардан фойдаланиш. -Т.: ЎзМУ, 2001. – Б.46.
10. Муртазаев Б.Ч. К вопросу изучения физико-географических процессов Юго-Западного Гиссарского хребта на примере Яккабогского лесничества Экономика и социум. №11 (102), 2022.-518-528 с.
11. Nazarov M.G. The variety of anthropogenic landscape and the scientific theoretical basis of their classification. American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development, 14, 127–132.
12. Назаров М.Г. Қашқадарё ҳавзасининг антропоген ландшафтлари ва уларнинг геоэкологик ҳолати // PhD дисс. автореферат. Самарқанд, 2020. 19 б.
13. Жумаев.Х.Х. Қашқадарё вилояти туризм - рекреация салоҳиятини баҳолаш ва туризм инфратузилмасининг ҳудудий тизимларини такомиллаштириш // PhD дисс. Самарқанд, 2022. 129 б.
14. Nazarov M.G. Facilities of landscapes of Uzbekistan and sustainable development //European science review. Scientific journal. № 2 2018–vienna (Austria)- P. 88-90.
15. Назаров М.Г., Муртазаев Б.Ч., Яхшибоев Б. Антропоген ландшафтларни тадқиқ-этишнинг илмий ва назарий асослари Экономика и социум.№3(94), 2022. -726-730 с.
16. Хўжамқулов Б. Е Китоб давлат геологик қўриқхонаси екотуризм объектлари сифатида «Ўзбекистонда туризм ва рекреацияни ривожлантиришнинг географик муаммолари ва имкониятлари» Республика илмий- амалий конференция материаллари -Қарши ш. 2021 йил 19 май
17. Ходжиматов А.Н. Tabiatdan foydalanishning geografik asoslari. Darslik. Т.: TDPU, 2022 112-113 б.
18. Ярашев Қ.С. Жанубий Ўзбекистон дарё ҳавзалари ландшафтларининг функционал-динамик боғлиқлиги ҳамда уларни ландшафт – экологик раёнлаштириш. Фан доктори (Dsc) дисс.автореф. Самарқанд, 2022.

19. Yarashev Q.S., Xasanov J.Yu., Qurbonova I.Z., Sadulloyeva L.K. World and uzbek experience in development of ecologic tourism //Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government Vol. 27, No. 6. 2021. <https://cibg.org.au/>
20. Ярашев Қ.С., Юсупов Б.Б., Очилов С. Тоғ ва тоғолди ландшафтларида экотуризм ривожлантиришининг айрим масалалари (Ҳисор давлат кўриқхонаси мисолида). \O'zbekistonda turizimni rivojlantirishda moddiy-madaniy yodgorliklar va muzeylarning o'rni (Qashqadaryo moddiy-madaniy yodgorliklari va muzeylari misolida) Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya 5-may, 2022-yil 49-55 b
21. Yusupov B.B., Экотуризм атроф муҳитни муҳофазалаш ва барқарор ривожлантириш омилли. «Zamonaviy geografik tadqiqotlar: nazariya, amaliyot, innovatsiya» Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya materiallari Samarqand sh, 12-13 may 2023 yil 151 B.
22. Ўзбекистон Республикаси экология, атроф-муҳитни муҳофаза қилиш ва иқлим ўзгариши вазирлиги ахборот хизмати бўлими.
23. Қашқадарё вилояти туризм ва спорт бош бошқармаси ахборот хизмати бўлими.
24. www.turizm.gov.uz